

THE CONCEPT OF PERCEPTION AND THINKING IN PSYCHOLOGY. ITS PRINCIPLES

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Abstract: This article provides detailed scientific and theoretical reflections on the concepts and principles of consciousness and thinking in humans.

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A person can express thoughts and feelings through actions and actions. However, in whatever form thoughts and feelings are expressed, all these means are ultimately translated into spoken language, which is, it is true, the universal means of all sign systems used by man for universal explanation. This important role of language in a number of communication systems is related to its direct connection with thinking, which is the source of all messages transmitted by any sign system. The close connection between thinking and language, their closeness leads to the most understandable expression of thought in language. Speech helps thoughts to acquire a clear content and a coherent form.

Folk wisdom says: "He who thinks clearly speaks clearly." Voltaire said that a beautiful thought loses its value if it is poorly expressed, and if it is repeated, it becomes boring. It is a language that helps to communicate the thoughts of people all over the world. Through language and writing, thoughts can be passed down to other generations. Perception and understanding of thought is not important in itself. They cannot be sensed in any way, they cannot be seen, tasted, touched or heard. The phrase "People communicate through speech" cannot be taken literally. The listener perceives the connection of words and understands their meaning, what the speaker wants to express - thoughts. This concept directly depends on how high the level of the listener or student is.

Consciousness is the highest level of logical understanding, an abstract, reflective, philosophical mind that works with broad generalizations and seeks a deeper understanding of reality.

According to E. Nikitin, thinking gets rid of the opposition of rational forms and gains freedom. In the sense of completeness and comprehensive understanding at the level of the subjective and objective mind, as well as in the understanding of the unity of thought in practical and theoretical senses, it becomes practically one. Knowledge at this level is the most profound and generalized. In this sense, mental consciousness is a deep dialectical process. The efficiency of thinking is directly related to previous experience, the actual evaluation of a person and mental abilities, which requires the ability to organize thoughts, feelings and actions in an acceptable way.

Everything here is directly related, and the more perfect this organization is, the more perfect the mind is. Mind, language, communication. At its core, language is the same as consciousness. Only humans are endowed with speech, and this is truly a miracle. None of the other living creatures can express their feelings and emotions, thoughts and situations

through the language function. If we give this concept a purely human understanding, animals do not have consciousness either. Animals do not have the function of speech, and they communicate with each other through some sounds that do not require speech.

The essence of language lies in its dual function. The first serves for communication, the second for thinking. Speech is an active process of communication, thoughts, feelings, desires, goals, etc., are carried out through language, in other words, a unique system of means of communication.

Language helps to turn the thoughts and feelings of each person into public property, not only for individuals, but also for the spiritual wealth of the whole world and society. Language also helps a person to perceive the world and the surrounding reality not only with the help of his senses and brain, but also through the brain and feelings of other people, which he was able to master with the help of language. The important role of language is that it becomes a mechanism of social heredity and thereby preserves the moral values of the society, and at the same time it is a material form of collecting and preserving the basic elements of human consciousness.

The exchange of ideas takes place with the help of language. There are only two ways of such an exchange: expression of thoughts. Understanding ideas. It is important to understand that perception has certain characteristics. Written things can be read and understood in different ways. It is characteristic of a person to express his thoughts through various means.

Mutual understanding occurs only when the listener's brain has the same idea about specific words for some reason, which often happens when translating from one language to another. In other cases, the ideas and thoughts expressed by the speaker are formed only in the images in the listener's head. This method of communication in science is called shama, according to this principle, the idea is not transmitted in speech, but appears in the mind of the listener. According to this principle, the result of communication is incomplete reproduction. Mind and language are connected to one another. In their composition, they determine each other according to the principle that the ideal composition determines the material form. Language is the work of thought and consciousness at the immediate level. In the process of thinking, language plays the role of a tool of the communication process. Thoughts are formed according to our language and fully correspond to it. However, it should be noted that the opposite statement is also true, because a person organizes his thoughts according to the logical line of thought.

B. Pasternak clearly explains the meaning of the unity of thought and word in expression: "The image of the world is revealed in the word." And Voltaire, when we get used to the idea, when the mind absorbs the thought, like Minerva, who emerged from the head of Jupiter in armor, is suitable. asserts that it emerges from the head clothed in words, fully armed with appropriate phrases. Consciousness and language are united by an organic link, which cannot be broken and both are destroyed. Language helps to move from perceptions and imaginations to concepts. This process is accompanied by the operation of concepts. A person uses the speech function to record his thoughts and feelings, so that he can analyze them and communicate them to other people. Expressing his thoughts, a person understands them more deeply, because he experiences the clarity of his words to others. Language and mind are one. This unity is determined by consciousness, thinking, because it is a reflection of reality, it creates forms and establishes the laws of its scientific existence. Through consciousness and practice, the structure of language or the structure of existence is reflected

in a renewed form. However, unity does not mean identity at all. Consciousness reflects reality and language acts as its symbol and transforms it into thought. Speech is not thinking.

According to Feuerbach, if speech is determined by thinking, all great speakers become the greatest thinkers. Language and consciousness act interdependently as contradictory units. Language affects the mind, its historically established norms characteristic of different peoples give different shades to the same subjects.

The style of the German philosophical culture is significantly different from the French philosophical system, and it is worth noting that these differences are the result of the specific characteristics of the languages of these nations. It is important to understand that the opposition of language and thought is not absolute. Some linguists believe that thinking is mainly determined by its relationship with reality, and language, in turn, partially changes the form and style of thinking. Language affects thinking, consciousness, and if it forces thought to do something, it shows the direction of action through the channels of language, thereby defining common boundaries for them, undergoing constant changes, having its own emotional color. . It's a simple thing that can be given to others. Everything cannot be expressed with the help of language. The secrets of the human heart hide many feelings and emotions, and this is where poetry, music, architecture and other forms of art come to the rescue. The process of obtaining information by a person occurs through language

A sign is an object, process, action that acts as a representative of something else in communication and is used as an object to receive, store, change or transmit information. Such symbol systems are formed and developed as material forms in which consciousness and thinking are realized, as well as information processes in society or in modern technology. Symbols indicate the information they convey. Meaning is expressed in the material form of a sign that reflects reality. It consists of sensory and emotional elements, voluntary impulses, requests, in other words, the field of psyche and consciousness. The simplest form of sign system is natural language. Non-linguistic copies are also sign systems. Here are photos, fingerprints, traces of fossilized animals or plants, signs (a rise in body temperature is a sign of illness, cloudy skies, the approach of rain), signs-signals (phone ringing, horn sound, clapping), signs- signs (the double-headed eagle is the symbol of the Russian state), communication signs - all elements of natural and artificial languages. Artificial systems are represented by, for example, Morse code or codes used in programming. This includes formula signs, diagrams, traffic signal systems, and more. Any character is unique only to its system. Explanation The science dealing with the structure and activity of sign systems is called semiotics. The need to develop gesture systems requires the development of science and technology, art and social practice. The use of symbolic systems greatly simplifies scientific research. Scientists will be able to get a lot of information using short formulas without using a standard language. In addition, this happens at the international level, which does not allow using a regular language. However, it should be noted that artificial language systems exist as additions to natural systems and are based on them. Language, together with its entire sign-symbolic system, does not have a sufficient meaning by itself. All the spiritual powers and limitless possibilities of human communication are aimed at communicating with the world and with those who can understand thought and language. This is only possible with an adequate understanding of availability. The problem of consciousness in its various forms has been described above.

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